

METHODS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract

As all language learners know, speaking is one of the skills that have to be mastered by students in learning English. Today we need English language almost in all spheres of our life including medicine, law, technology, agriculture and etc. Improving the speaking abilities of students has always been a concern as it is an essential tool for communicating. There are different techniques to develop students' speaking ability. This article aims to discuss a number of effective methods and techniques as well as Project-Based Learning available for teachers to enhance the students' speaking skills which allow them to work autonomously and with creativity. Modern pedagogy is expected to educate oral speech of target language fast, interestingly and more effectively. For this purpose, this paper analyzes the importance of speaking skills. Also, it focuses on introducing some productive methods and activities for teachers.

Keywords: Project Based Learning, Speaking Ability, Oral speech skills, pedagogical technologies, communicative approach, Communicative Language Teaching, Direct Method, Total Physical Response.

INTRODUCTION

English language is an international language and it is a language which is mostly used. English is playing a major role in many sectors including medicine, engineering, education, advanced studies, business, technology, banking, computing, tourism, and soon. All our software development today, the communication facilities available to us through internet, our access to a variety of websites, are all being carried out in English. Most of the research works are conducted and compiled in English.

In learning English, speaking seems intuitively the most important skill because it is a productive skill in the oral mode which can show the learners' output. From the students' speaking performance, teachers can see what students have achieved from the learning process and what aspects need improvement. As Nunansaid, mastering the art of speaking is the most important aspect of learning a language. Uragrees that —of all the four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing), speaking is the most important skill. Anything written and recorded in this language is read and listened to, in wider circles. As a result, English is being taught and learned around the world as a second language today. Speaking is "the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts" (Chaney, 1998). Speaking is a crucial part of second language learning and teaching, it's an art of communications and one of 4 productive skills, that must be mastered in learning foreign language. Good speaking skills are the act of generating words that can be understood by listeners. According to Brown and Yule (1983), speaking is the skill that the students will be judged upon most in real-life situations. It is an important part of everyday interaction and most often the first impression of a person is based on his/her ability to speak fluently and comprehensively. So, teachers have a responsibility to prepare the students as much as possible to be able to speak in English in the real world outside the classroom. Despite its importance, for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as a repetition of drills or memorization of dialogues. However, today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills, because, only in that way, students can express themselves and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative circumstance. Every day teachers are getting access to some new technologies, which join hand with English teaching. As the conventional teaching method such as the chalk and talk method seem to be outdated, the modern technologies and techniques can be used as

a supplement to the classroom teaching methods to have a lively atmosphere in the classroom. New technologies in language learning by multiple intelligence and mixed abilities replace with old methods of teaching. In relation to the importance of speaking skills in language learning, the teacher will have a big responsibility to help the students to speak English as much as possible.

The teachers who teach English seem to have greater responsibility in their teaching experiences because to speak English is considered to be a difficult task for students. The students recognize English as the language that they do not use every day. For them it is a new thing to speak English and they find some difficulties in speaking English. There are some problems faced by students in speaking. First, the students do not have adequate vocabularies, so they are afraid of expressing their ideas. Then, the students cannot pronounce the words correctly and it makes them feel embarrassed and it can increase their anxiety to speak because they are afraid of making mistakes. Besides that, the students are less motivated in the classroom. As a result, they do not engage actively in the learning process. Considering the difficulties faced by students in speaking English as a foreign language, motivation has an important role in the learning process. Learner who has high motivation to learn English will almost always be successful in the learning itself.

There are some categories that can be used as the role of learners in developing speaking skills in the classroom (Brown, 1994):

Intensive - It goes one step beyond imitative to include any speaking performances that are designed to practice some phonological or grammatical aspects of language.

Responsive - It consists of short replies to teacher- or student-initiated questions or comments.

Transactional (dialogue) - Transactional language, carried out for the purposes of conveying or exchanging specific information, is an extended form of responsive language.

Interpersonal (dialogue) - It carried out more the purpose of maintaining social relationship than for the transmission of a fact and information. These conversation are a little trickier for learners because they can involve some or all of the following factors - a casual register, colloquial language, emotionally charged language, slang and sarcasm.

Extensive (monolog) - Here the register is more formal and deliberative. It can be planned.

There is no single way to teach English. There have been lots of approaches in teaching speaking. These are a few of the top ESL teaching methods used in the classroom today, including:

Direct method

For the direct method, all teaching is done in the target language, translations are not allowed in class, and the focus lies heavily on speaking instead of grammar. This makes the direct method a very student-centered strategy that has gained popularity in recent years.

Students are supposed to learn the target language naturally and instinctively, which is why the direct method is also called the “natural approach.” Mistakes are corrected as they happen in class, and teachers reinforce the correct usage of the language with praise. This method is frequently used when teaching English online, as many virtual ESL companies require teachers to only speak English during class. Communicative language teaching (CLT)

Communicative language teaching is perhaps the most popular approach among the methods of teaching ESL today. CLT emphasizes the students' ability to communicate in real-life contexts, and students learn to make requests, accept offers, explain things, and express their feelings and preferences.

Since CLT focuses on teaching language through real-world assignments and problem-solving, it's less concerned with grammar accuracy and instead focuses on fluency.

Total physical response (TPR)

You may have heard of this teaching strategy for ESL before, but what exactly is TPR? Total physical response has become a very popular approach in which students react to the teacher with movement, such as miming, gesturing, or acting out the language.

For example, the teacher and students might make an exaggerated frown and pretend to cry when learning the word “sad.” TPR suggests that students learn the target language best through physical response rather than by analysis.

TPR is often used when teaching English online and when teaching young learners, as it not only helps students remember vocabulary but also provides an outlet for their energy and helps them stay focused when sitting for long periods of time.

If you like TPR, you might also like using drama as an ESL teaching method.

An eclectic approach

Many teachers choose from the collection of humanistic approaches (TPR, for example) and communicative approaches (the direct method and CLT), as well as many other teaching strategies for ESL learners, and use what works best for them. For example, a teacher who uses mostly the direct method may occasionally do a lot of grammar explanation when teaching a test preparation class, or a CLT advocate may borrow some aspects of the direct method or use TPR.

Task-/project-/inquiry-based learning

This teaching strategy for ESL students can sometimes be considered a part of CLT, but it heavily emphasizes the students' independence and individuality.

Inquiry-based learning is a modern approach that is becoming widely popular in schools all over the world. By asking questions and solving problems, with the teacher as a mere learning facilitator, student motivation and participation in tasks and projects are thought to increase.

Why is task-/project-/inquiry-based learning important?

During task-based learning, students solve tasks that are relevant and interesting to them. In order to solve the task, they need to use the target language they're learning to communicate with their peers. They use authentic language instead of answering grammar or vocabulary questions about the language. Students—especially younger learners don't actually feel that they're studying a language at that moment because they're engrossed in the task they're working on.

Task-based learning is especially conducive to group learning. Learning a language as a group is also a very important contributor to effective retention. Collaborating with others and becoming confident with the language within a group is a key step in acquiring that language. Also, receiving positive feedback from peers and teachers increases confidence and motivation to learn and to communicate with others.

Students' understanding of the language also deepens because the realistic context in which they're learning the language is relevant to their personal lives. It's a good idea to ask your students about their hobbies and preferences at the beginning of a course so that you can include their interests in the tasks you set.

In addition to the benefits for students, solid knowledge of this method will also increase your job prospects as a teacher. Some job ads specifically ask for task-based language teaching experience!

What is task-/project-/inquiry-based learning method?

The task-based teaching approach is one of many modern ESL teaching methods and focuses on setting a goal for students this could be a report, a video, or a presentation and then following three main steps to achieve that goal.

The pre-task

During this stage, which can take up a whole lesson if needed, the teacher introduces the task to the students and gets them motivated to solve it. Once everyone is engaged, the teacher should explain what is expected for the task.

Verbalexplanationscanbesupportedbyanexamplefromtheteacherorbyshowinga previousstudent'swork.Theteachercanthengivefurtherinstructionsifneededandoffera dviceonhowtoapproachthetask.

The task

This isthe mainstage of task-basedlearning, where studentsstart workingon the task, usually in groups or pairs. This stage is done in the target language sothat students feel the need to use the language they want to learn in order to solvethetask.

Theteacherdoesn'tusuallyjoinintheworkprocess.Instead,heorshewillmonitorthe studentsandofferhintsifstudentsreallyneedsupport.

Thereview(orpost-task)

Once the students have completed the task and have something to present, thereviewstage,alsoknown asthepost-task,starts.

It's a good idea to let students evaluate each other's work and only offer ateacher review of frequently-made errors during the task. Peer correction could becarried out in the form of comments, feedback discussions, or a checklist withadditionalroomforfreecommentary.

The reviewstageoffersstudentstheopportunitytoreflectontheirworkandanalyzeitinorderto improvetheirskills forthefuture.

Whatisa task(vs.anactivity)?

Task-basedlearningusesalessonstructurethatincorporatesdifferentactivities to solve a task. The task can span the length of an entire lesson or, if it'sproject-basedlearning,itcantakeupseverallessons tocomplete.

Essentially,thetaskisthebig-pictureassignmentthatstudentsaretryingtocomplete or solve, and the activities are the individual steps or exercises they taketoachievethe task.

Examplesoftasks include:

Creating a presentation

Making a video or short movie

Writing a piece of text, such as a newsletter article

Acting out a skit

Creating an original game that includes writing down the game rules, playing the game, and evaluating the game

Working out the solution to a practical problem, such as planning an upcoming trip or gathering missing information, like working out who started a rumor at school

Participating in a group debate or discussion, like arguing for a favorite competitor in a TV show. You can develop some great tasks using these fun ESL games and activities for young learners and teens.

What is a task-based activity?

A task-based activity is a procedure in which students have to use the target language in order to achieve a specific outcome. The best TBL activities reflect real-life situations, so the students can see that the lesson is relevant to their own lives.

One of the main task-based learning advantages is that the activities allow students to use the language they know freely and exploratively as long as they are able to complete the overall task. Error correction can be done at the end of the lesson if necessary but not during the activity, so you encourage fluency and motivate students to use the language.

An example of a task-based activity could be to have each student draw a comic picture and explain the content and the inspiration behind it to the group. They then have to collaborate to put together a comic strip that includes each student's picture, which is the main task (to create an original comic strip).

Conclusion

Using interesting and effective methods and techniques in learning a second language has become a real necessity nowadays. This article has reviewed briefly different

effective methods which can be utilized in developing the speaking skill of the learners. Different methods for using technology in improving speaking skill were discussed thoroughly. As a result, the following concluding recommendations can be recorded:

Theory and practice in second language learning can be matched together by the use of modern methods.

Modern techniques should be followed for effective learning and teaching of the speaking skill.

English language teachers should encourage their students by using different methods in developing their speaking skill.

Modern technological tools are much more interesting and provide fun and enjoyable learning, motivating the students, and help them to enhance their language learning in a fruitful way. Moreover, these tools help students learn at their own pace and promote autonomy in them.

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